

EFFECTIVENESS OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS IN SCHOOL PRACTICE

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Abstract. *The leading place in the system of pedagogical research for obtaining scientific information is occupied by the observation method. The main function of this method is the selective perception of information about the phenomenon being studied, the process using direct and feedback connections. Almost any empirical research should begin with an analysis of literature, documents and observation of existing experience on the problem being studied. The observation method can be used either independently or in combination with other methods.*

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The diagnostic methods used in pedagogical research should ensure the selection of an effective system of ways to solve problems in operational management and allow one to establish the dynamics of the development of certain qualitative characteristics.

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It is important to remember that through observation it is almost impossible to obtain data about the hidden characteristics of people's behavior, such as their values, orientations, and motives.

The validity and reliability of an observation method largely depends on the accuracy of recording, the situations, facts and processes described.

The most common method in pedagogical research is the survey method, the essence of which is to obtain answers to the questions asked. The main source of information received is a verbal oral message, statement, judgment of the interviewed student, teacher, parent (legal representative). During the survey, the researcher can obtain important information about the state of the educational process, trends in its development, etc.

There are three main types of survey: questioning (written face-to-face and correspondence survey), interviewing (oral conversation, survey), sociometric survey.

Questioning is widely used because to make it possible to obtain the necessary information about the object being studied in a very short time. It is important to remember that questionnaires must always be completed personally by respondents. The questionnaire should be a questionnaire in which the questions are presented in an orderly manner by form and content. The reliability of the information obtained during the survey depends on the design of the questions. In this regard, it is necessary to comply with certain requirements when formulating them.

The interviewing method is used in organizational and pedagogical research, in particular in the development of programs for managing the development of educational systems at various

levels. There are two main types of interviews: standardized - implies strict adherence to the purpose, content and form of asking questions, and non-standardized - characterized by greater flexibility in goals, content covered, form and number of questions asked. To obtain reliable information during an interview, it is necessary to provide the respondent with psychological comfort [2].

The conversation method is used to identify the personal characteristics of the subject, his motivational, emotional, intellectual, adaptive and other characteristics. Conversation is almost always combined with other methods: observation, experiment, hardware and technical methods. Research by the conversation method presupposes the presence of a conversation goal, a plan, a group of main plot questions, as well as reinforced and supporting ones. When conducting a conversation, the researcher is required to be able to establish and maintain contact with the respondent. The process and content of the conversation must be recorded in the form of a transcript, voice recorder, tape recorder, or video. The results obtained by the conversation method are practically not amenable to formalization and statistical processing. Based on the conversation data, one can characterize the state of the phenomenon or object under study.

It is necessary to compare these results and relate them to other methods to obtain the most reliable information.

The testing method is widely used in pedagogical practice. With the help of tests, you can assess a student's initial readiness for learning, level of training, intellectual capabilities and other characteristics. It should be remembered that testing only shows the state of the properties (characteristics) being studied, without showing the features and conditions of their formation and development. Repeated use of tests in practice contributes to a more accurate assessment of the subject.[3]

Analysis of activity products. This method allows the teacher to obtain psychological information about students based on a skillful analysis of their regular academic work. For example, analysis of the results of a test in mathematics, drawings, drawings allow one to draw a conclusion about the level of development of thinking, knowledge and skills of the student.[7]

Very often, when getting to know students, essays are used, which, to a greater extent than questionnaires, are able to reveal attitudes towards academic subjects, types of free time activities, hobbies, and other aspects of life. For example, by analyzing essays, one can establish not only the presence of cognitive interests, but also, to some extent, the level of their awareness, the degree of emotional involvement, the nature of cognitive interests, as well as get an idea of literary abilities, vocabulary, and imaginative thinking.

Pedagogical diagnostics provides the study of the educational process, helps to identify the prerequisites, conditions and results of the pedagogical process in order to optimize it and justify its results for the development of society (K. Ingekamp, 1968). At the same time, he proposes to understand pedagogical diagnostic activity as a process during which, observing the necessary scientific criteria, the teacher observes students and conducts questionnaires, processes observation and survey data and reports the results obtained in order to describe behavior, explain its motives or predict behavior in future.[9]

The effectiveness of pedagogical diagnostics is the correlation of the results obtained with the goals and past achievements in educational practice.

The algorithm for studying the effectiveness of the diagnostic process can be presented as follows:

- defining the purpose and objectives of the study;
- selection of criteria and indicators to determine the effectiveness of the pedagogical process of students;
- choice of study methods;
- preparation of diagnostic tools;
- research of subjects;
- processing and interpretation of research results;
- analysis, evaluation and discussion of the study results.

In order to more clearly and in detail present the content and methods of activity of the organizers and participants of the diagnostics, it is necessary to consider some stages of the diagnostic process.

Selection of criteria and indicators. This stage is one of the most important, since it defines specific characteristics and indicators that allow further making informed judgments about the effectiveness of the process. The content of criteria and indicators of the effectiveness of the pedagogical process is determined by a set of goals and objectives solved by the school team or an individual teacher. Each goal and objective must be supported by a certain set of criteria and indicators, on the basis of which one could judge the success of the implementation of targets.

Selection of study methods. Work at this stage should be started only after determining the criteria and indicators of the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. The selection of methods should not be random - they must be selected in accordance with selected criteria and indicators. Currently, a significant number of diagnostic techniques have already been accumulated that can be used in the research and practical activities of teachers; diagnostic techniques can be adapted or new ones developed to diagnose a specific pedagogical problem.[8]

The observation method allows you to get an idea of how students behave in the classroom, how they perceive and comprehend the material being studied, to what extent they show intelligence and independence in developing practical skills, what are their learning inclinations, interests and abilities, degree their perseverance and regularity in acquiring knowledge. The accumulation of a sufficient number of observations makes it possible to determine the individual characteristics of students, take them into account in their work and, therefore, take a more objective approach to testing and assessing students' knowledge.

The effectiveness of the questioning method lies in the fact that the teacher asks students questions about the material studied and, by evaluating the answers, determines the degree of its mastery. A holistic answer allows us to reveal the depth of knowledge and the completeness of assimilation of their logic. However, being an effective method of monitoring students' knowledge, used by teachers in almost every lesson, oral questioning also has its drawback, since it requires a significant investment of time and allows you to test the knowledge of no more than 3-4 students during a lesson [10].

The effectiveness of the conversation method lies in obtaining a large amount of student information. Conversations reveal the students' attitudes, their feelings and intentions, assessments and positions. This research method is distinguished by the teacher's purposeful attempts to penetrate into the student's inner world and identify the reasons for certain of his actions. Information about moral, ideological, political and other views, and their attitude to problems of interest is also obtained through conversations. But conversations are a very complex and not always reliable method. Therefore, it is most often used as an additional method to obtain the

necessary clarifications and clarifications about what was not clear enough during observation or the use of other methods.

Conclusion. Reform of the goals and content of higher education requires solving the problem of the quality of education, since new requirements for specialists and graduates are in conflict with the current diagnostic system for the quality of student training.

Diagnostics is of great importance for the targeted and effective implementation of the educational process. It allows, through control (monitoring) and correction of the entire system of education and training and its components, to improve the process of education, training and development.

The activities of the teacher and diagnostic activities are inseparable. As you know, any pedagogical intervention (whether it be training or education) must be preceded by a diagnosis, therefore any teacher, and especially a class teacher, must be proficient in pedagogical diagnostics. In the system of educational work, all the methods of diagnosing knowledge discussed above should be used in order to ensure the necessary systematicity and depth of control over the quality of students' performance.

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